

Research of Terminological Systems of Vocabulary Units

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Abstract. *The article deals with the terminological system of lexical units related to bread, the interaction of language units with each other, the interrelationships between them, the essence of each unit in any system due to connections, and the relationship between units of the same system, lexical units, language units (phonemes, morphemes, lexemes, etc.) appear in speech in a specific material form, and lexical units related to bread are analyzed in terms of lexical-semantic groups in terms of synonymous, antonymic, and homonymous relationships.*

Key words: *lexeme, system, lexical unit, term, event, system, dictionary, language, lexicon, phoneme, morpheme, historical-etymological, hyponymy, antonym, synonym, semantic, field terms.*

I. INTRODUCTION

It is known that the vocabulary of the Uzbek language is the vocabulary and lexical-semantic system of this language formed as a whole phenomenon. But it should also be taken into account that the vocabulary of our language has developed in a very complex way during its historical development. The historical development of the vocabulary of any language and in order to know the features of the formation of words contained in the vocabulary of a given language study from an etymological point of view, determine their genesis and source of origin is required. Such studies, in turn, in the past of the Uzbek language, brother and allows us to determine the interaction with unrelated languages and historical development that took place in the vocabulary of the language, grammatical constructions prepares the ground for a scientific understanding of its processes.

Linguists analyze the vocabulary of this language from a historical and etymological point of view. When they do this, their main goal is to identify their own and borrowed words. E. Begmatov writes about this: "The method of dividing words into historical and etymological groups can also be studied with the help of this method is a dictionary, which consists of the vocabulary of the language. Genetic sources of units, that is, what linguistic element the word actually is allows us to determine. "Enrichment of lexical content occurs mainly in two ways, that is, the creation of words based on the Uzbek language.

Occurs through mastering the vocabulary of foreign languages. Internal sources are the main source of enrichment of the vocabulary of the Uzbek language. Bread internal source in the formation of terms (with affixation, composition and semantic method word formation) occupies a special place. The terms of this layer are written in the Uzbek language itself. It is formed on the basis of its phonetic, semantic and grammatical rules. V. P. Danilenko as a term in the field of science and technology to the circle of commonly used words also includes the names used, and they are the same both in common use and in terminology. Designation only by types of meanings, content and information capacity he mentions the difference baking, military, folk games, sheep breeding, yearling, botany, mathematics.

II. Experimental methods

Terminology of dozens of areas, such as physical education and sports, medicine, medicine, chemistry, musicology, anatomy, jewelry, carpentry, gardening, road construction. At the same time, the terms baking technology refer to the profession that preceded them. Are included in many official terminology systems containing words. these words "appearing in any field of activity, over time, with the development of science" turned into terms".

J. Sager identifies three main features of the concept of "terminology": a) activity: the process of collecting, describing, standardizing, presenting and disseminating terms; b) theory: hypotheses, methods that describe and study the relationship between a concept and a term and results; y) dictionary (lexicon): dictionary of a special area (concepts). It depends on the size of the bread, its taste and other characteristics. Are divided into types. Each of them is represented by the corresponding terms. From the point of view of synonymous, antonymous and homonymous relations of related lexical units. It is divided into lexical-semantic groups and analyzed. Linguistic units (such as phoneme, morpheme, lexeme) in speech in a certain material form.

III. Development of oral speech skills

Accordingly, the names of breads are also lexemes. Language units with each other by introducing mutual connections, relationships between them, connections in which system the essence of each unit is not the unit itself, but the same is determined by the relationships between the units of the system. The subject matter of lexemes and lexical-semantic groups have a number of common features. Language units, lexemes are distinguished by entering into three types of relationships: a) similarity (paradigmatic) relationships; b) hierarchical (hierarchical) relationships; c) neighborhood (syntagmatic) relationships.

A complete terminological system of lexical units associated with bread in the Uzbek language. The history of the formation of terms in this area in the course of research as a system, together with the study of lexical-semantic groups, methods of formation, sources of enrichment along with the question of determining their substantive connection, i.e. terms was transverse. Terms specific to the material of the object of study have the following meanings.

Hyponymy of lexemes. Analysis of the system of a lexical unit associated with bread in relation to a number of terms included in its composition as a result of committing it turned out that they are interconnected. After all, "A thing in reality, a sign, features connections are very common. Such connections are found in nature, and in life, and in science. We also often meet." The same is in the bakery terminology of the Uzbek language. It is clear that the situation has found its expression. Baking concepts based on their species characteristics, it should be noted that these are mainly "varieties", Together with the concepts of "type", "kind", "taste", "color" it forms a single whole. All such concepts acquire a real form in the language through special lexical units.

As a result, a whole terminological system is formed. And these are all components of terminology - such terms as "variety", "kind", "kind", "taste", "color". It is obvious that it exists. Each of these semes represents a field as a hyponym. Because they represent a series of interconnected lexical units, or rather, consists of terms.

Patronymics of lexemes. In the meaning of the name of everything living and nonliving that exists in nature from objects to completely man-made objects it acquires integrity from the connection and attachment of certain parts. Such dialectic correlation can be seen in the example of "parts" of "bread" and the "whole" piece, they, although in small quantities, are represented by specific terms in the lexeme of bakery products. Expressed, it is often used, especially among experts.

IV. Activity monitoring

Antonyms of lexemes. Baked goods according to the analysis of materials antonymous due to the fact that the lexical unit has its own characteristics in expressing concepts, from the terminology of other areas antonymic pair consisting of individual lexical units in contrast less applicability was observed.

Synonymy of lexemes. When studying the vocabulary of the Uzbek language from the point of view of the system. The issue of synonymy is also important. "The meaning a complete and thorough study of their relations, - say H. Nematov and R. Rasulov. In their monograph - the scheme of expression in the lexical scheme of the Uzbek language... is an important factor that creates opportunities for learning. This includes, among other things, the following occurs." The number of such topics is as follows: in the second paragraph it is indicated: "2) semes that determine the scope of use of the lexeme ("to colloquial speech characteristic", "bookishness", "sublimity", "unusualness", "characteristic of the poem", "a certain category" characteristics of speech (argot, slang)", "characteristics of the dialect", etc." We call this term "lexemic". We considered it necessary to add the term ("characteristics of the lexeme"). Because this is what you mean the originality of the research method based on the synonymy of terms, the synonyms of which are given stands out. In this regard, synonyms are considered as a wealth language. There is a difference in terminology. When studying synonyms in this area of linguistics, be guided by the principle of selection. Is done, that is, the principle of "one concept - one term" is observed. The purpose of studying synonyms in terminology is to use their synonyms.

According to Kodukhov, "the word is forgotten." The released internal form can be reanimated ... if special attention is paid to it. In the Uzbek linguoculture, many linguistic units have been created about bread. Because people as the sage said, the history of mankind consists of bread and wandering around it.

For example, in the culture of the Uzbek people to see a piece of bread or even a piece of bread on the ground when it remains, immediately pick it up from the ground and kiss it, then put something under the fire a national tradition of putting it away, for example, in a hole in the wall. Bread choir in such situations, elders say that "bread that breaks bread is bread, and he who crushes it becomes bread for the blind." Similar ideas are common to all three languages.

National and cultural aspects of terms. Narrowing the meaning is one of the most effective ways to create terms. In industry terminology there are terms formed in the same way. According to Kodukhov, "the forgotten internal form of the word is special for him. If you focus... you can revive it." Bakery technology intermediate position between unmotivated and motivated terms in terminology possessive terms are also present, and they do not completely lose their internal form.

V. Conclusion and Recommendation

In the Uzbek language, there is a term "darmon bread", that is, dried protein from chickpea flour. Healing bread is such because it serves to strengthen human health. Is called In addition, the internal form of the term "wedding bread" is mutton sprinkled with sesame. If it means preparation, the internal form of the term is "layering" - layer by layer. Is observed during preparation. So, etymological dictionary comments, proverbs. If we are talking about phraseological units, then we can understand the internal form of the term. As a result, the lexical semantics of the language unit is understood by the symbol based on the name. When it comes to rich sources of industry terms, simple language and the phrase should be distinguished from colloquial words and phrases. Simple language units "in general". In general, not only the literary language, but also the communication of people speaking the literary language.

This also contradicts the colloquial language. In Uzbek: obi non, kuk non, cha-chap non, shappati.

Non-verbal combinations have the characteristic of a word or phrase used in simple language. It is known that some categories of vocabulary, including the internationalization of terminology. Russian language consists of Greek-Latin morphemes and only Greek and Latin elements. These are names. It consists of international morphemes. Complete with the terminology of baking technology, including the following terms relevant.

USED LITERATURE

1. Abdiev M.B. System analysis of field lexicon. - T.: A.People's heritage named after Kadiri. 2004. -110 p.

2. Abdullaev T.A. Crafts of Uzbekistan of the XIX–XX centuries – Vol., 1976. - 40 p.
3. Abdullaev F. On some issues of the lexicon of the Uzbek language//A.C.Works of the Pushkin Institute of language and literature. Book one. Materials from the grammar of the Uzbek language. - T., 1949. – P. 87-102.
4. Apresyan Yu.D. Lexical semantics. Synonymous means of language. – M.: nauka, 1974. - 367 p.
5. Humboldt V. Selected works on linguistics. M., "Progress", 1984, 502 p.
6. Dal V.I. Explanatory dictionary of the living Great Russian language. At 4 part, St. Petersburg, 1863, 1866.
7. Kolesov V.V. Ancient Rus: heritage in the word. Book 3. Genesis and Genesis. St. Petersburg, Faculty of Philology of St. Petersburg State University, 2004, 400 p.
8. Likhachev D.C. the Great Way. The formation of Russian literature of the XI – XVII centuries, Moscow, Sovremennik, 1987, 301 p. (Library of "Lovers of Russian Literature").
9. Tursunov U. Issues of Uzbek terminology. - T.: Uzdavnashr, 1933. - 39 p.
10. Shoabdurahmanov Sh., Askarova M., Hajiev A., Rasulov I., Daniyurov H. Current Uzbek literary language. - T., 1980. - 448 p.
11. Shoabdurahmanov Sh. Uzbek literary language and folk dialects. The interaction between the dialects of the base city and the modern Uzbek literary language. - T.: Science, 1962. -371 p.